

Analysis of differences in results of breathing resistance between testing laboratories

After conducting interlaboratory comparative tests and exchanging test protocols, differences in the results of determining breathing resistance may be detected. Thus, using the example of the test results of filtering half masks PP "Lepestok" 201 FFP2 NR, we will conduct an analysis. The results indicated below are data obtained by two testing laboratories, the names of which are not disclosed, but we designate them as laboratory No 1 and No 2. The purpose of the analysis is to identify the reasons that became the source of the differences obtained.

Problem definition.

According to the interlaboratory comparative testing program, it was planned to determine the breathing resistance on samples at a static air flow with flow rates of 30 and 95 l/min.

The EN 13274-3:2005 standard "Respiratory protective devices – Methods of test – Part 3: Determination of breathing resistance" provides for the possibility of using two schemes for such determination (Fig 1).

Figure 1. Testing schemes for determination of breathing resistance according to EN 13274-3:2005: 1 – adjustable airflow; 2 – sample; 3 – sample clamp; 4 – flow meter; 5 – aspirator (vacuum pump); 6 – manometer

At the same time, the EN 149:2003 standard "Personal respiratory protective equipment. Filtering half masks for protection against aerosols. Requirements, testing, marking" specifies the procedure for determining breathing resistance on the Sheffield dummy (human head dummy), i.e. scheme b should be used.

The testing laboratory No 1 uses exactly such a scheme (on a head dummy), and laboratory No 2 uses scheme a), i.e. in a clamp.

There is a need to determine the influence of the scheme used on the convergence of the results obtained.

Analysis.

The obtained test results for determining breathing resistance (in mbar) are presented in test reports, but for ease of processing they are converted to Pa.

Laboratory testing results			
No 1		No 2	
30 l/min	95 l/min	30 l/min	95 l/min
18	63	31	89
17	60	30	92
19	62	28	95
16	57	31	84
16	55	31	87
18	56	32	92
17	59	31	94
17	57	27	86
16	60	30	88

Let's estimate the difference between the two laboratories' results for each flow rate.
for a flow rate of 30 l/min. for a flow rate of 95 l/min.

31	18	13
30	17	13
28	19	9
31	16	15
31	16	15
32	18	14
31	17	14
27	17	10
30	16	14
Average		13

89	63	26
92	60	32
95	62	33
84	57	27
87	55	32
92	56	36
94	59	35
86	57	29
88	60	28
Average		30,88889

Let's calculate the coefficient of the ratio of the differences in air flow rates:
 $30.88889/13=2.376068$. This coefficient is necessary due to the increase in flow rate from 30 to 95 l/min.

Let's calculate the difference between the laboratory indicators taking into account the coefficient:

Calculated differences	26	10,94245
	32	13,46763
	33	13,88849
	27	11,36331
	32	13,46763
	36	15,15108
	35	14,73022
	29	12,20504
	28	11,78417
Average	30,88889	13
Coefficient	2,376068	

So, we get the same value of the difference between the results in 13 Pa.

Let's check the theory about coefficients.

Let's check the conversion coefficient for the results of both laboratories.

The coefficient for the equipment of the laboratory No 2 is already known as 2.376068. Then, the coefficient for the laboratory No 1 will be:

	30 l/min	95 l/min	Calculated coefficient
Result	18	63	3,5
	17	60	3,529412
	19	62	3,263158
	16	57	3,5625
	16	55	3,4375
	18	56	3,111111
	17	59	3,470588
	17	57	3,352941
	16	60	3,75
Average	17,11111	58,77778	3,441912

So, let's calculate the correlation coefficient:

For laboratory No 1 is $3.441912/2.376068 = 1.448575$.

For laboratory No 2 is $2.376068/3.441912 = 0.69171$.

Thus, using the correlation coefficient, we recalculate the data, we get:

for laboratory No 1

Laboratory testing results			
30 l/min		95 l/min	
Without correlation	Including correlation	Without correlation	Including correlation
18	26,07434	63	91,2602
17	24,62577	60	86,91447
19	27,52292	62	89,81162
16	23,17719	57	82,56875
16	23,17719	55	79,6716
18	26,07434	56	81,12018
17	24,62577	59	85,4659
17	24,62577	57	82,56875
16	23,17719	60	86,91447
17,11111	24,78672	58,77778	85,14399

And for laboratory No 2

Laboratory testing results			
30 l/min		95 l/min	
Without correlation	Including correlation	Without correlation	Including correlation
31	21,44301	89	61,56218
30	20,7513	92	63,63731
28	19,36788	95	65,71244
31	21,44301	84	58,10363
31	21,44301	87	60,17876
32	22,13472	92	63,63731
31	21,44301	94	65,02073
27	18,67617	86	59,48705
30	20,7513	88	60,87047
30,11111	20,82815	89,66667	62,02332

Conclusions.

1. Testing laboratories use different schemes for determining breathing resistance and different equipment, which leads to differences in the results obtained. The introduction of a correlation coefficient allows you to adjust the obtained data and obtain reproducibility in inter-laboratory tests.

2. The laboratory No 2 does not take into account the system's own resistance in the calculations, which is 13 Pa and introduces an error in the results obtained.